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**PREVALENCE OF DIABETES MELLITUS
AMONG OUTDOOR PATIENTS**

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ABSTRACT:

Diabetes mellitus (DM), commonly known as diabetes, is a group of metabolic disorders characterized by a high blood sugar level over a prolonged period of time. Symptoms often include frequent urination, increased thirst, and increased appetite. If left untreated, diabetes can cause many complications. This cross-sectional study was conducted among outdoor patients presenting in different hospitals. The sign, symptoms, and levels of random blood sugar (BSR) was noted. All the data was entered and analyzed with SPSS Ver. 23.0. There were 90 patients that were included in this study. The mean age of the patients was 36.23 ± 5.3 years. There were 50 (55.6%) males and 40 (44.5%) females included in this study. All the patients presented with different symptoms i.e., increased thirst, increased urination, or increased food intake. Out of 90 patients, 21 were suffering from diabetes mellitus II. Out of these 21 patients, 9 were aware of this and were taking the medication.

KEYWORDS: DIABETES MELLITUS

INTRODUCTION:

Diabetes mellitus (DM), commonly known as diabetes, is a group of metabolic disorders characterized by a high blood sugar level over a prolonged period of time. Symptoms often include frequent urination, increased thirst, and increased appetite. If left untreated, diabetes can cause many complications. Acute complications can include diabetic ketoacidosis, hyperosmolar hyperglycemic state, or death. Serious long-term complications include cardiovascular disease, stroke, chronic kidney disease, foot ulcers, damage to the nerves, damage to the eyes and cognitive impairment. Diabetes is due to either the pancreas not producing enough insulin, or the cells of the body not responding properly to the insulin produced.

Type 1 diabetes must be managed with insulin injections. Prevention and treatment of type 2 diabetes involves maintaining a healthy diet, regular physical exercise, a normal

body weight, and avoiding use of tobacco. Type 2 diabetes may be treated with medications such as insulin sensitizers with or without insulin. Control of blood pressure and maintaining proper foot and eye care are important for people with the disease. Insulin and some oral medications can cause low blood sugar. Weight loss surgery in those with obesity is sometimes an effective measure in those with type 2 diabetes. Gestational diabetes usually resolves after the birth of the baby.

As of 2019, an estimated 463 million people had diabetes worldwide (8.8% of the adult population), with type 2 diabetes making up about 90% of the cases. Rates are similar in women and men. Trends suggest that rates will continue to rise. Diabetes at least doubles a person's risk of early death. In 2019, diabetes resulted in approximately 4.2 million deaths. It is the 7th leading cause of death globally. The global economic cost of

diabetes related health expenditure in 2017 was estimated at US\$727 billion. In the United States, diabetes cost nearly US\$327 billion in 2017 (1-3). The objective of this study was to see the prevalence of diabetes mellitus among the outdoor patients presenting in different hospitals.

MATERIAL OF METHODS:

This cross-sectional study was conducted among outdoor patients presenting in different hospitals. The sign, symptoms, and levels of random blood sugar (BSR) was noted. All the data was entered and analyzed with SPSS Ver. 23.0. The quantitative variables were presented as mean and standard deviation. The qualitative variables were presented as frequency and percentages.

RESULTS:

There were 90 patients that were included in this study. The mean age of the patients was 36.23 ± 5.3 years. There were 50 (55.6%) males and 40 (44.5%) females included in this

study. All the patients presented with different symptoms i.e., increased thirst, increased urination, or increased food intake. Out of 90 patients, 21 were suffering from diabetes mellitus II. Out of these 21 patients, 9 were aware of this and were taking the medication.

DISCUSSION:

There is no known preventive measure for type 1 diabetes. Type 2 diabetes—which accounts for 85–90% of all cases worldwide—can often be prevented or delayed by maintaining a normal body weight, engaging in physical activity, and eating a healthy diet. Higher levels of physical activity (more than 90 minutes per day) reduce the risk of diabetes by 28%. Dietary changes known to be effective in helping to prevent diabetes include maintaining a diet rich in whole grains and fiber, and choosing good fats, such as the polyunsaturated fats found in nuts, vegetable oils, and fish. Limiting sugary beverages and eating less red

meat and other sources of saturated fat can also help prevent diabetes. Tobacco smoking is also associated with an increased risk of diabetes and its complications, so smoking cessation can be an important preventive measure as well.

The relationship between type 2 diabetes and the main modifiable risk factors (excess weight, unhealthy diet, physical inactivity and tobacco use) is similar in all regions of the world. There is growing evidence that the underlying determinants of diabetes are a reflection of the major forces driving social, economic and cultural change: globalization, urbanization, population aging, and the general health policy environment. Diabetes management concentrates on keeping blood sugar levels as close to normal, without causing low blood sugar. This can usually be accomplished with dietary changes, exercise, weight loss, and use of appropriate medications (insulin, oral medications). Learning about

the disease and actively participating in the treatment is important, since complications are far less common and less severe in people who have well-managed blood sugar levels. Per the American College of Physicians, the goal of treatment is an HbA1C level of 7-8%. Attention is also paid to other health problems that may accelerate the negative effects of diabetes. These include smoking, high blood pressure, metabolic syndrome obesity, and lack of regular exercise. Specialized footwear is widely used to reduce the risk of ulcers in at-risk diabetic feet although evidence for the efficacy of this remains equivocal (4-6).

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